

THE DESIGN OF AXIAL FLOW CANISTERS FOR CARBON DIOXIDE ABSORPTION

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Summary

Design data and guidelines are presented to help predict and maximize the performance of axial-flow carbon dioxide canister designs using alkali metal hydroxide absorbers. The design data are derived from a series of laboratory tests conducted at the Naval Coastal Systems Center to isolate the effects of environmental and geometric parameters on canister absorption efficiency. A sample canister design is considered to demonstrate the use of the derived data to predict effective canister life.

Introduction

The Navy has a vital interest in indentifying improved techniques, or more efficient methods, for removing metabolically produced carbon dioxide from divers' life support equipment. The inability of the CO₂ absorbent to maintain an acceptably low level of carbon dioxide, within the severe environmental conditions seen by divers, has been one of the major obstacles in the development of improved breathing apparatus.

Efficient removal of carbon dioxide is an absolute requirement for any acceptable closed-circuit breathing system. Generally, this is accomplished by passing the diver's expired gas through a fixed bed of granular material which has a strong affinity to CO₂. Although all one-man, closed-circuit systems rely on this general method for CO₂ removal, important differences exist in system geometry and flow behavior between the various systems. Unfortunately, these differences make it extremely difficult to predict the performance of a new system given only information about related existing systems. Our prediction capability is further complicated when new operational performance requirements (i.e., depth, temperature, etc.) are introduced for existing systems or systems being developed. Through necessity, a "cut and try" approach has been utilized when developing a new absorber system. Since diving technology is continually moving into previously inaccessible conditions of service, it is imperative that reliable techniques be developed to simulate and predict the performance of CO₂ absorbers.

It is not always an easy task to predict how a canister will function in a particular environment. Since World War I, when chemical absorbing agents were being investigated for gas masks,¹ engineers have been asking how the absorption efficiency of their CO₂ "scrubbers" can be optimized. What are the most favorable environmental conditions for efficient operation of the absorption canister? How does the geometry of the canister effect this efficiency? Can we predict the performance of a CO₂ scrubber under one flow condition based on our observations of its performance under different flow conditions?

The data in this paper has been developed in an effort to help answer these questions, as well as, help engineers to predict the performance of prototype canister designs. Most design information in this paper is related to the absorption characteristics of High Performance Sodasorb, manufactured by W. R. Grace Co. This information is derived from a series of laboratory tests^{2,3,4,5} conducted between FY 80 and FY 82 to isolate the effects of various

environmental parameters on absorption efficiency.

Design Considerations for CO₂ Scrubbers

Many factors which affect the performance of carbon dioxide scrubbers are beyond the control of the designer. For instance, the operational pressure and temperature are usually fixed by the diver's surroundings. Any efforts to operate the scrubber in conditions other than his surroundings must be made at the expense of large expenditures of energy and involve complex designs.

However, maximum efficiency of the carbon dioxide absorbent can be obtained by following several general design guidelines as summarized in Figure 1.⁶ They include the following:

FIGURE 1. THE ABSORPTION PROCESS

1. MAXIMIZE THE GAS RESIDENCE TIME WITHIN THE CANISTER: In so doing the carbon dioxide in the gas stream has the greatest opportunity to be absorbed by the chemical absorbent. In constant flow systems the residence time can be maximized either by increasing the canister length (a trade-off with canister flow resistance) or by reducing the gas velocity within the canister. The flow velocity can be reduced either by providing a large cross-sectional area within the canister, or by controlling the volumetric flow rate actually going through the canister. For example, bypassing a portion of the gas stream around the canister can effectively reduce this flow rate within the canister while still maintaining an acceptable CO₂ level after mixing downstream of the canister.

In intermittent flow systems, such as those using the pumping action of the breathing cycle, the dead volume within the canister should be made as large as the human tidal volume to maximize absorption efficiency. In so doing the gas from the previous exhalation can reside in the canister during the entire inhalation phase. An intergranular space of approximately 0.5 litres is adequate for resting conditions with up to 3.5 litres required for maximum work rates.

2. MATCH THE SCRUBBER DURATION WITH THE OXYGEN STORAGE CAPACITY: The scrubber duration should be adequate to match the expected oxygen consumption by the diver, as dictated by the diver's respiratory quotient (RQ). For a typical RQ of 0.85 the diver would be required to absorb 0.85 litres of CO₂ for each litre of oxygen consumed. A breathing apparatus designed with a system RQ greater than 0.8 to 1.0 (has an excess scrubber capacity) would give a breathing apparatus which would deplete its oxygen source prior to canister breakthrough. An apparatus with

where t_{TH} is the theoretical time to consume all active absorbent in the canister, resulted in the following functional representation of canister performance:

$$\eta = f(\text{Re}, T, H, \frac{e}{D}, \frac{L}{D}) \quad (2)$$

where

Re = Dimensionless Reynolds number based on absorbent particle diameter.

$$= \frac{\rho V e}{\mu}$$

Note that we have been able to reduce the 15 original functional parameters into six dimensionless groups.

TABLE 1

PARAMETERS INVOLVED IN CANISTER CO₂ ABSORPTION

Parameter	Identification	Dimensions
t_B	Breakthrough Time	t
V	Gas Stream Velocity	L/t
T	Gas Temperature	T
ρ	Gas Density	m/L ³
μ	Gas Viscosity	m/Lt
C	CO ₂ Concentration	L ³ /L ³
H	Gas Stream Water Vapor Content	L ³ /L ³
HA	Absorbent Water Content	L ³ /L ³
W	Absorbent Mass	m
e	Particle Size	L
L	Canister Length	L
D	Canister Diameter	L
D_v	Mass Diffusivity	L ² /t
A	Absorption Capacity	m/m
R	Reaction Rate	m/t

<u>Basic Units</u>	
t	= Time
L	= Length
m	= Mass
T	= Temperature

In so doing we have been able to reduce the imponderable mathematics of Equation 1 to a more manageable characterization of six dimensionless groups.

Data from a large series of carefully controlled laboratory tests^{2,3,4,5} were handled in the manner described above and plotted in Figure 2. These data show the effects of particle Reynolds number, and canister geometry on the efficiency of a canister to absorb carbon dioxide. All data are based on steady flow through axial canisters.

FIGURE 2. CALCULATED EFFICIENCY OF STANDARD TEST CANISTER AT VARYING PRESSURES

To use this data to design new canisters or to predict the life of present canisters in varying environmental conditions, we can enter Figure 2 on the abscissa or ordinate depending on the constraining conditions being put on the design. If the system flow rate is known at the depth of interest, the Reynolds number (based on absorbent particle diameter) can be calculated. This Reynolds number can then be used to obtain a canister efficiency, η , corresponding to the appropriate operating pressure. The theoretical bed life can then be read from Figure 3, for a specific weight of absorbent, to allow us to calculate a predicted canister life as

For CO₂ concentrations diff from 1%
Divide theoretical bedlife from chart
by % CO₂ (SLE)
Bedlife based on 0.01 ata (1% SLE)
CO₂ in system flow

FIGURE 3. THEORETICAL BEDLIFE FOR SODASORB CANISTERS

$$t_B = t_{TH} \eta \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, if a specific canister life is desired, the previously obtained value of η can be used to calculate the necessary theoretical bed life as

$$t_{TH} = t_B / \eta \quad (4)$$

Figure 3 can then be used to determine the mass of absorbent required for this canister life requirement.

The empirical relationship for the efficiency of a standard canister

$$\eta_{STD} = 1 - 0.94e^{-\frac{P+1}{\left(\frac{Re}{P}\right) 1.3\sqrt{P}}} \quad (5)$$

where

P = environmental pressure (atmospheres absolute)

Re = Reynolds number based on absorbent particle diameter

has been found to closely represent the data in Figure 2. This equation can be used to derive a canister efficiency once the Reynolds number of the system flow and the ambient pressure is known.

Note that this derived efficiency is for a saturated gas stream at 21.1°C (70°F) with a canister length-to-diameter ratio and diameter-to-mesh ratio of 7 and 2.75, respectively. For conditions and/or canister geometries other than these, modifying coefficients, as shown in Figures 4 through 8, must be considered to calculate the canister efficiency under actual flow conditions.

FIGURE 4. TEMPERATURE EFFECT FACTOR, A_T

FIGURE 5. HUMIDITY EFFECT FACTOR, A_H

FIGURE 6. CO₂ INJECTION RATE FACTOR, A_C

FIGURE 7. LENGTH-TO-DIAMETER EFFECT FACTOR, A_D

FIGURE 8. WALL EFFECT FACTOR, A_F

The easiest way to explain the use of these charts of test data and modifying coefficients is to demonstrate their application in a sample test canister.

Sample Calculations

An axial flow canister 37.5 cm (14.75 in) long by 15.25 cm (6-in) inside diameter is filled with 5.4 kg (12 pounds) of 4 by 8 mesh HP Sodosorb. What is the predicted life of this canister when 153 liters/min (5.4 ACFM) of a heliox mix with 0.58 percent (SLE) carbon dioxide flows through at an ambient pressure seen at 119 metres (390 feet) of seawater?

The predicted life of this canister can be arrived at by multiplying the theoretical canister life, t_{TH} , by the canister efficiency, η , as

$$t_B = t_{TH} \cdot \eta$$

From Figure 3, we can find the theoretical life of a canister with 12 pounds of HP Sodosorb which sees 5.4 ACFM of 1-percent CO₂ laden gas to be approximately 790 minutes (13.2 hours). As directed in this figure we divide this bed life by the actual percent concentration of CO₂ for levels other than 1 percent. Thus, the actual theoretical bed life will be

$$t_{TH} = \frac{790 \text{ minutes}}{.58} = 1,362 \text{ minutes (22.7 hours)}$$

We next arrive at the expected canister efficiency through the use of Figures 2 and 4-8. To enter these charts we must first determine the mean particle Reynolds number, Re , for the canister absorbent material, where

$$Re \equiv \frac{\rho \bar{v}_e}{\mu}$$

- \bar{V} superficial gas stream velocity in the canister, ft/sec
- e mean absorbent particle diameter, feet
- ρ, μ the gas stream density and viscosity, respectively.

From the US Navy Diving-Gas Manual¹⁰ an acceptable breathing mixture at 119 metres of seawater (12.8 ATM) would be 84 percent helium/16 percent oxygen with the following gas properties

$$\rho = 4.16 \text{ kg/m}^3 \text{ (0.26 lbs/ft}^3\text{)}$$

$$\mu = 2.13 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s (1.43} \times 10^{-5} \text{ lbs/ft-sec).}$$

The superficial gas stream velocity is determined by dividing the gas flow rate by the canister cross-sectional area

$$\bar{V} = \frac{5.4 \text{ ft}^3/\text{min}}{\frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{6}{12}\right)^2 \text{ ft}^2} \times \frac{1 \text{ min}}{60 \text{ sec}} = 0.46 \frac{\text{ft}}{\text{sec}}$$

The mean particle diameter of 4 by 8 mesh Soda-sorb (see Table 2) is 0.14 inch. We can now calculate the particle Reynolds number according to the above definition to get

$$Re = \frac{.26 \text{ lbs/ft}^3 \times .46 \text{ ft/sec} \times .14/12 \text{ ft}}{1.43 \times 10^{-5} \text{ lbs/ft-sec}}$$

TABLE 2
PARTICLE MESH SIZES

TYLER MESH RANGE	MESH OPENING INCHES	MEAN PARTICLE DIAMETER, INCH
4-8	.187 - .093	0.140
8-20	.093 - .033	0.063
10-20	.067 - .033	0.050
20-60	.033 - .010	0.022
32-60	.020 - .010	0.015

$$Re = 97.6$$

and $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D} = 97.6 \times \frac{14.75}{6.0} = 240.$

We can now enter the bottom of Figure 2 with a value of $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D}$ of 240 to arrive at a value for the canister efficiency at 12.8 ATM under the standard conditions shown in the legend, i.e.,

- 100% RH incoming gas humidity
- 70°F incoming gas temperature
- 1% CO₂ level in incoming gas
- 6.5-7.0 length-to-diameter ratio of canister
- 2.75 canister-to-particle diameter ratio.

For this value of $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D}$ we get approximately

$$\eta = 0.23$$

For this example we will assume that the incom-

ing gas stream is 60°F and saturated with water vapor. The canister L/D ratio is 2.5; the canister-to-particle diameter ratio, D/e, is 43; and as stated previously, CO₂ concentration is 0.58 percent SLE.

The canister efficiency under these conditions is found by multiplying the standard canister efficiency, η , by the correction factors from Figures 4 through 8 for conditions which vary from the standard, i.e.,

$$\eta_{\text{ACTUAL}} = \eta_{\text{STD}} \cdot A_T \cdot A_H \cdot A_C \cdot A_D \cdot A_F$$

where

A_T = Temperature Effect Factor

A_H = Humidity Effect Factor

A_C = CO₂ Injection Rate Factor

A_D = Length-to-Diameter Effect Factor

A_F = Wall Effect Factor.

A_T for 60°F and $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D}$ of 240 is 1.0 (Figure 4). A_H is also 1.0 since it is identical to the standard canister (also see Figure 5). A_C is approximately 1.9 for a CO₂ level of 0.58 percent SLE (Figure 6). A_D and A_F are seen to be 1.0 in Figures 7 and 8 for $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D} = 240$. Therefore,

$$\eta_{\text{ACTUAL}} = 0.23 (1.0)(1.0)(1.9)(1.0)(1.0)$$

$$= 0.437$$

and the predicted canister life will be

$$t_B = t_{TH} \cdot \eta_{\text{ACTUAL}}$$

$$= 1,362 \text{ min} \times 0.437 = 595 \text{ min (9.9 hrs).}$$

The canister and flow conditions described in the previous example are similar to those seen by the Navy's MK 12 Surface Supported Diving System. This system is designed to operate at a maximum depth of 390 FSW while supplying 6 ACFM to the diver's helmet (5.4 ACFM are recirculated through the CO₂ canister while 0.6 ACFM is exhausted from the helmet). In excess of 10 hours system duration was reported for the MK 12 CO₂ scrubber at 390 FSW when the inlet gas temperature was maintained above 60°F.¹² During these unmanned tests a simulated diver work cycle was given by 6 minutes injection of CO₂ into the canister at 0.75 percent SLE (moderate work rate) followed by 4 minutes injection of CO₂ at 0.33 percent SLE (rest). This gave a mean injection rate over a 10-minute period of

$$\% \text{ CO}_2 \text{ mean} = \frac{6 \times .75\% + 4 \times .33\%}{10}$$

$$= 0.582\%$$

Discussion

The close agreement between the predicted canister life and the experimentally recorded duration of

the MK 12 canister under similar operational conditions is encouraging. A shortcoming of this predictive method, however, is seen when we attempt to look at how the canister life will drop off as the gas stream temperature is decreased (a phenomenon recorded experimentally for the MK 12 canister). Figure 4 shows a decreasing temperature effect factor, A_T , as temperature is decreased when values of $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D}$ are less than approximately 56. This would suggest that the effect of temperature is minimal when $Re \cdot \frac{L}{D}$ is greater than a value of 56 (sample canister had a value of 240). The shortcoming of this design data is not understood. It could potentially result from the use of data derived from small, isothermal canisters to predict the performance of relatively large canisters with known bed temperature variations. Further experience with the use of these charts will be necessary before it can be determined whether this shortcoming is universal or only peculiar to the MK 12 design.

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